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A model-based framework for the quality assessment of surface albedo in situ measurement protocols

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ABSTRACT

Satellite-based retrievals of land surface albedo are essential for climate and environmental modelling communities. To be of use, satellite-retrievals are required to comply to given accuracy requirements, mainly achieved through comparison with in situ measurements. Differences between in situ and satellite-based retrievals depend on their actual difference and their associated uncertainties. It is essential that these uncertainties can be computed to properly understand the differences between satellite-based and in situ measurements of albedo, however quantifying the individual contributions of uncertainty is difficult. This study introduces a model-based framework for assessing the quality of in situ albedo measurements. A 3D Monte Carlo Ray Tracing (MCRT) radiative transfer model is used to simulate field measurements of surface albedo, and is able to identify and quantify potential sources of error in the field measurement. Compliance with the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) requirement for 3% accuracy is tested. 8 scenarios were investigated, covering a range of ecosystem types and canopy structures, seasons, illumination angles and tree heights. Results indicate that height of measurement above the canopy is the controlling factor in accuracy, with each canopy scenario reaching the WMO requirement at different heights. Increasing canopy heterogeneity and tree height noticeably reduces the accuracy, whereas changing seasonality from summer to winter in a deciduous forest increases accuracy. For canopies with a row structure, illumination angle can significantly impact accuracy as a result of shadowing effects. Tests were made on the potential use of multiple in situ measurements, indicating considerably increased accuracy if two or more in situ measurements can be made.

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1. Introduction

Land surface albedo is one of the Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) defined by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) in collaboration with the United Nations

Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) GCOS [11,12], and determines the fraction of shortwave radiation absorbed by the land surface. Surface albedo is a controlling factor for atmosphere–plant–soil flux interactions at the surface, affecting precipitation, evapotranspiration, temperature, and cloud formation [5]. Relationships between surface albedo and temperature [51], climate sensitivity [9], drought [15], fires [33] and human activity [31] have been studied extensively.

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Given the significance of surface albedo, and its interactions with the climate and human activities, land surface albedo must be measured in the temporal and spatial scales required for climate modelling, environmental and ecosystem research. Satellite-based retrievals of land surface albedo have been shown to be able to extract albedo at the temporal and spatial scales required. Various satellites have provided or are currently providing land surface albedo products, including Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) [29,48], Multi-angle Imaging SpectroRadiometer (MISR) [6], Landsat Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager (SEVIRI) [1], Satellite Pour l'Observation de la Terre (SPOT) VEGETATION (VEG) [13], GlobAlbedo [35], Meteosat [42] and Global Land Surface Satellite (GLASS) albedo products [32] to name but a few. All of these products provide albedo products in a number of spatial and temporal resolutions, as well as spectral resolutions focusing on visible, near-infrared (NIR) or shortwave broadband albedo (BBA) products, and albedo under specific illumination characteristics; bi-directional hemispherical reflectance (BHR_{iso}) which assumes complete diffuse irradiation, directional hemispherical reflectance (DHR) which assumes energy is coming only from direct sunlight and bi-directional reflectance (BHR) which is a combination of the two.

Comparing these land surface albedo retrievals with ground measurements is fundamental for assessing the accuracy of the products [4] and improving retrieval algorithms. Comparison studies between global land surface albedo products and in situ measurements have demonstrated that differences exist between the two measurements. Suggested reasons behind these differences include scale mismatch [4], upscaling tower measurements to satellite footprint [45], heterogeneity of the land surface [22] and spatial representativeness of in situ validation sites [46], retrieval algorithms for albedo from space [28], cloud and atmosphere correction [49] and solar angle [31]. While in situ measurements are widely considered as the reference for validating remote sensing products, they also contain uncertainties, caused by a wide variety of environmental and experimental factors, which along with the uncertainty of remotely sensed data, can contribute to the observed differences. However, it is difficult to separate the contribution of uncertainty of the in situ measurement from that of the remotely sensed product, due to the multi-stage nature of satellite-based retrievals and the fact the true value of target quantity is generally unknown [34]. Following the extensive work accomplished by the metrology community in providing a standard for quality assessment of metrological measurement systems or processes, it is necessary that the remote sensing community is able to do the same for both the Earth Observation (EO) products and the in situ measurements, facilitating the provision of trustable and traceable uncertainty information, so that the differences between EO and ground measurements can be fully understood.

Monte Carlo Ray Tracing (MCRT) radiative transfer models have long been used to simulate land surface products [47,36,37,27], and can provide an alternative method to assess the assumptions and simplifications

made during their retrieval [60], as they provide a 'virtual laboratory' in which conditions and experiments can be heavily controlled. In addition to satellite-based products, if the field measurement protocol and instrument design is known, MCRT models are also capable of simulating in situ measurements for products such as surface albedo, Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation (FAPAR) [53] and Leaf Area Index (LAI) [39], and can be used to quantify uncertainties arising solely from the in situ measurement protocol. Given that in field it is difficult to set up controlled experiments that can assess uncertainty without unaccounted-for influences in the measurement, MCRT models are able to offer an alternative method for providing unbiased traceable quality assessments of in situ measurements protocols.

This paper presents the development of a model-based quality assessment framework that allows the quantification of uncertainty for in situ measurements of broadband albedo (DHR) within vegetation canopies. A 3D MCRT radiative transfer model is used to simulate field measurement protocols for albedo in a variety of complex vegetation canopies. Two main sources of uncertainty are investigated, firstly the field measurement protocol, i.e. the placement of an albedometer within the vegetation canopy and its height above the canopy, and secondly, intrinsic factors of the scenario considered, such as canopy structure (landscape heterogeneity, leaf area density (LAD) and fractional coverage), tree height, ecosystem type, season and illumination geometry. A brief introduction on MCRT models and the model used in this study, canopies and scenarios considered and simulation of surface albedo field measurements are described in Section 2. Results are displayed in Section 3 and then discussed in Section 4. Finally, concluding remarks on this study are presented in Section 5.

2. Methods

2.1. Monte Carlo ray tracing (MCRT)

3D MCRT radiative transfer (RT) models are used in optical canopy reflectance modelling to describe the scattering of shortwave radiation in complex 3D vegetation canopies. In brief, MCRT models solve the radiative transfer equation within a canopy by tracing 'rays' propagated from a source to the sensor (forward) or from the sensor to the source (reverse), tracing the collisions of photon trajectories with elements in the canopy [8]. 3D MCRT models define a canopy as a set of scatterers, each with specific interaction model that defines how radiation is scattered, absorbed and transmitted, where the location, orientation, size and shape of each scatterer must be known [16]. Describing a canopy in such a way is a complex problem that requires effective sampling schemes, where Monte Carlo (MC) sampling methods have been demonstrated to be an effective method of stochastically sampling the scattering phase function of the individual scatterer. Many MCRT models have been developed to simulate various types of remote sensing instruments, including satellite instruments that measure top-of-canopy bidirectional reflectances [47], LIDAR [7], flux measurements such as FAPAR [53] and LAI

[10]. They have allowed the investigation of impacts of illumination and viewing angle on reflectances, on canopy structure, such as leaf angle distribution (LAD), leaf size or leaf/canopy clumping, on the simulation of sensor response functions and the impact of topographic effects. They have also been used in the benchmarking of simpler models [8], such as the RAdiative-transfer Model Intercomparison (RAMI) exercise [40,41,62,61].

This study uses **raytran** [16,17,55], an MCRT model that typically works in the forward mode, tracing rays from the source through all interactions and finally either to absorption or exiting the canopy. An arbitrarily complex scene is described in terms of geometric principles with corresponding interaction properties, and can therefore be described independently from the model. **Raytran** has been tested against both field measurements and goniometer measurements [16,17] and with other radiative transfer models in the RAMI benchmarking exercise [40,41,62,61,60,56].

To simulate radiative processes, **raytran** requires the description of the illumination characteristics of the scene, an architectural description of the scene based on geometric principles, and the spectral characteristics of all the scattering elements within the scene. The architectural description of the scene can be made independently from the radiative transfer problem, and is defined in terms of geometric principles such as sphere, cylinders, discs etc, which are then grouped together into objects such as leaves, needles, branches, twigs and trees, which ultimately form a scene. All these principles can be associated with reflectance and transmittance properties and a scattering law, thus determining the type of interaction that will occur when a ray intersects the element (absorption, reflectance or transmittance) and if necessary, the new direction of travel of the ray. Finally, an illumination source must be defined, where rays are generated from a source, and their trajectories followed from interaction to interaction. **Raytran** has been used to simulate a series of different measurements, including surface reflectances [19], surface albedo [15,18], radiative fluxes [54,59], FAPAR [53] and LAI [41]. Additionally, **raytran** is not only capable of simulating top-of-canopy reflectances, but also in situ measurements.

2.2. 3D canopies

3D vegetation/forest canopies were chosen so that they covered various ecosystem types, tree planting patterns

(regular or random), canopy structure and season. The canopies are highly detailed canopy representations based on actual inventory data collected, totaling 8 different scenarios described in Table 1 which encompass a range of ecosystem types, seasons, and canopy structural parameters. Each canopy was taken or based on the RAMI-IV 'actual-canopy' phase [56]. For each canopy, structural and spectral information were required for each individual leaf/needle, twig, branch and trunk, as well as information on the soil and/or understory and tree placement structure within the canopy.

For each canopy, fractional coverage, LAD and a landscape heterogeneity index are computed to attribute canopy structural parameters for each scenario. LAD is defined as the total one-sided leaf area per unit of horizontal layer where the average LAD within the entire canopy is computed from Leaf Area Index (LAI) divided by the height (h) of the canopy ($LAD=LAI/h$). Following RAMI-IV definition, fractional coverage is computed as 1-direct transmission at solar zenith angle of 0° or nadir. A canopy heterogeneity parameter is computed using the Rahman–Pinty Verstraete (RPV) model [44], which performs the decomposition of a BRDF field into 3 parameters; one of which is κ , otherwise known as the Minnaert function parameter. Considering that the directional pattern of solar radiation in the red spectral wavelength is mainly controlled by the geometric arrangements of the elements within the canopy [43], the κ parameter in the red spectral domain (κ_{red}) was demonstrated to quantify the degree to which the angular variations in the BRDF field represent a bowl- or bell-shaped pattern [14]. The former pattern occurs in the presence of dense quasi-homogeneous or sparse tree coverage, and can be defined by a $\kappa_{red} < 1$. The latter pattern on the other hand occurs in the presence of clumped or heterogeneous foliage structures, and is defined by $\kappa_{red} > 1$. Accordingly, the methodology outlined in Widłowski et al. [57,58] was used; for each canopy, BRDF was simulated using **raytran** with an illumination angle of 30° and optical properties from a perfect red band (656 nm) assigned as leaf reflectance (transmittance) of 0.018 (0.021), a bark reflectance of 0.251 and a soil reflectance of 0.126, then κ_{red} obtained using an inversion of the RPV model, to assign a measure of canopy heterogeneity for each scenario.

The first canopy, a Wellington Orchard Citrus canopy is based on a field campaign conducted by Stuckens et al. [50] during 2006/2007 in Wellington, South Africa.

Table 1

Scenarios considered for this study, their associated season, the source of information and Solar Azimuth (SAA) and Solar Zenith (SZA) angles considered.

Scenario	Canopy	Season ^a	Source	SAA (°)	SZA (°)	κ_{red}	Fractional coverage	LAI	LAD
1	Citrus orchard	Spring	RAMI-IV	0	0	1.511	0.392	2.691	0.653
2	Citrus orchard	Winter	RAMI-IV	0	20	1.511	0.392	2.691	0.653
3	Citrus orchard	Summer	RAMI-IV	0	50	1.511	0.392	2.691	0.653
4	Citrus orchard	Spring	RAMI-IV	90	20	1.511	0.392	2.691	0.653
5	Citrus orchard (20% removed)	Summer	Generated	0	50	1.254	0.230	2.219	0.539
6	Citrus orchard (tree height)	Summer	Generated	0	50	0.421	0.489	1.590	0.141
7	Birchstand	Summer	RAMI-IV	270.7	36.6	1.190	0.504	3.442	0.135
8	Birchstand	Winter	RAMI-IV	291.3	54.0	0.711	0.251	0.0346	0.004

^a For citrus canopies, the season corresponds to the illumination angles used.

Fig. 1. Leaf reflectance and transmittance (full and dotted line), soil and bark spectra used for optical properties of citrus orchard canopy scene elements for input into *raytran*.

From these field measurements, virtual tree models were created using the *arbaro* software [52] to develop 10 *Citrus sinensis L.* unique tree models, each with unique spectral and structural characteristics. The canopy scene is $108.25 \times 103.9 \text{ m}^2$ with a maximum tree height of 4.12 m. The regular tree spacing pattern was modelled by placing a total of 1115 of the 10 unique trees in rows along the Y-axis at 2 m spacing, with an inter-row distance of 4.5 m. To replicate missing trees in the rows, 11% of the tree positions were excluded. The background was modelled as a dry Luvisol, corresponding to the main soil type found during the field campaign. Citrus leaf and bark reflectance were measured using a field spectroradiometer, where the spectra are plotted in Fig. 1, alongside the soil reflectance.

Four illumination angles were selected to highlight row structure impacts, as defined in Table 1, where 0° solar azimuth angle (SAA) defines the sun shining across the rows, and 90° SAA down the row, demonstrated in Fig. 2. These four illumination angles represent scenarios 1, 2, 3 and 4. Table 1 indicates that the canopy structure has a highly clumped pattern with a $\kappa_{red} > 1$ at 1.511.

The citrus orchard canopy formed the basis for two further scenarios designed to investigate the impact of row spacing in this regular tree pattern canopy (scenario 5) and of tree height (scenario 6). The former scenario, designed to examine the impact of row spacing, was created by randomly removing 20% of the trees. For the latter scenario, the 10 unique *Citrus sinensis L.* trees used in scenarios 1–5 were replaced with a single tree with a tree height of 11.27 m, i.e. almost three times the height of the original trees. This tree was based on a Linden (*Tilio cordata*) tree, modelled by Kuusk et al. [26] derived from a field measurement campaign in Estonia. This tree was selected on the basis that the mean crown radius for the 10 unique citrus tree models ranged from 0.61 to 0.82 m (with a mean of 0.74 m), and the Linden tree had a mean radius of 0.79 m, therefore is slightly larger than the mean of the citrus tree models. Illumination angles for these two canopies were chosen at SAA of 0° , and solar zenith angle (SZA) of 50° . Fig. 3 shows a schematic representation of these 3 versions of a citrus

Fig. 2. Overview of illumination angles considered for citrus orchard canopy with respect to the row structure.

orchard canopy, where the left top and bottom panels represent the citrus canopy considered for scenarios 1–4, the middle top and bottom panels demonstrate scenario 5 and the right top and bottom panels scenario 6. κ_{red} values for scenarios 5 and 6 are 1.254 and 0.421, where scenario 5 is still dominated by a clumping structural pattern, however as κ_{red} is reduced compared to scenarios 1–4, the canopy tends more towards an open canopy. The canopy structure of scenario 6 is explained by a low κ_{red} values, indicating that the increase in tree height and small increase in tree radius tends towards a more homogeneous closed-canopy structure.

The 7th scenario corresponds to a birchstand boreal forest canopy based on measurements made by Kuusk et al. [26,24,25] in Järvelja, Estonia. The virtual trees were generated by Kuusk et al. [26], using allometric equations for crown radius and length, and tree height, then each single tree constructed using the *xfrog* software Lintermann and Deussen [30]. The canopy scene is $105.5 \times 106.2 \text{ m}^2$ with a maximum tree height of 25.49 m, and total of 1029 trees. In the original scene described in RAMI-IV, 18 individual tree representations were generated in *xfrog*, however to maximise efficiency of computations, some of the larger trees within the scene were replaced by slightly smaller ones of the same species. Tree locations and number of trees were kept the same. Foliage and bark spectra were measured for each species using the UAVspec spectrometer. Ground reflectance was measured similarly at 9 points in the canopy, constituting a mix of both soil and understory vegetation, where the spectra of foliage (top panel), bark (middle panel) and ground (bottom panel) reflectance are demonstrated in Fig. 4. A single illumination angle scenario was defined, where SZA is 36.6° and SAA is 270.7° (see Table 1). The top panels in Fig. 5 show a schematic of this canopy.

The final scenario (scenario 8) was based on the same birchstand canopy introduced above, however during the winter season. In this canopy, all foliage elements were removed from all deciduous trees in the canopy, leaving

Fig. 3. Illustration of citrus orchard canopy architecture for scenarios 1–4 (left panels), scenario 5 (middle panels) and scenario 6 (right panels).

foliage elements only for the Norway spruce tree (bottom panels in Fig. 5), of which there were 39 out of 1029 total trees. The ground reflectance was classified as a typical snow reflectance spectra (dashed line in bottom panel of Fig. 4), and lambertian scattering assumed. κ_{red} values of 1.190 and 0.711 for scenarios 7 and 8 respectively indicate that canopy structure changes from a clumped heterogeneous structure during summer to an open sparse tree coverage structure during the winter.

It is important to note that while these canopies are highly detailed canopy representations of actual data, they are not identical to the real world canopies on which the 3D representations are based on. Despite the intensive field campaigns conducted to gather the wealth of information that exists so far, gaps in the information arise, including the individual shape, orientation and curl of the foliage elements, the individual spectral properties of the foliage elements, the shape and pattern of the twigs and branches, the reflectance and spatial variability of the background and the individual spectral properties of each twig, branch and trunk to name a few. Despite these information gaps, these 3D canopy representations provide a ‘virtual laboratory’, within which simulated sensors can be placed both outside and within the canopy, allowing us to simulate field measurements and their associated uncertainties and also test any assumptions made during the field measurement protocol.

2.3. *In situ* albedo measurements

In the field, *in situ* measurements of albedo are mainly computed using an albedometer composed of two pyranometers: one facing downwards to measure outgoing surface radiance and another facing upwards to measure incoming solar radiation. Albedo is then calculated as the ratio between the outgoing surface radiance and the incoming solar radiance. It is a broadband instrument, measuring approximately between 300 and 3000 nm. For the highest quality instruments (secondary standard albedometers) that are used in global networks of albedo measurements such as Fluxnet [3], Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN) [38], Aeronet [21] and Surface Radiation Budget Network (SURFRAD) [2] the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) states a maximum error of 3% for hourly measurements and 2% for daily measurements, where all albedometers must comply with this value to be used to validate EO albedo products World Meteorological Organisation [63].

WMO provides some recommendations as to where or how high albedometers should be placed in the canopy, for example for surfaces covered by short grass, the albedometer should be placed 1–2 m above the surface, for a forest canopy to have a tower of 30 m and when snow exists on the ground the surface, the albedometer height must be altered. However, recommendations have not yet

Fig. 4. Foliage (top panel) and wood (middle panel) reflectance spectra considered in scenarios 7 and 8 for the various trees within the scene, and soil and snow (bottom panel) reflectance spectra considered for scenarios 7 and 8 respectively.

been developed for each of the many difference scenarios that are experienced during field measurements.

2.4. Experimental set-up

Raytran is equipped with the capability to simulate flux measurements using virtual box-shaped voxels that measure the number of rays entering in and out of the top, bottom and lateral sides of the box. The top and bottom surfaces of the voxel are square, with a user-defined width, and the lateral surfaces rectangular, with a user-defined height. A broadband albedometer is therefore simulated by measuring the incoming fluxes entering the top of a virtual voxel, F^\downarrow (top pyranometer) and the incoming fluxes entering the bottom of a virtual voxel, F^\uparrow (bottom pyranometer). 125 spectral wavelength bands were chosen in the 400–2500 nm broadband range as the optimum number of bands to use to simulate the broadband instrument. Bands were computed using an optimisation procedure that reduces the amount of spectral bands required to compute broadband albedo to within 1% in comparison to a reference BBA computed from high

spectral resolution albedo. The albedometer instrument measurement is then simulated using Eq. (2), following the steps:

1. Computing spectral albedo under specific illumination conditions ($\alpha(\lambda, \theta, \phi)$) as the ratio of incoming flux into the bottom voxel, F^\uparrow , with the incoming flux entering the top voxel, F^\downarrow , as in Eq. (1):

$$\alpha(\lambda, \theta, \phi) = \frac{F^\uparrow(\lambda)}{F^\downarrow(\lambda)} \quad (1)$$

2. Weighting $\alpha(\lambda, \theta, \phi)$ with solar spectral irradiance spectrum (E^\downarrow) taken from ASTM:E-490 AM0 standard [20].
3. Weighting the calculated albedo with the albedometer spectral response $SR(\lambda)$ [23].
4. Applying a weighting factor for each wavelength resulting from the optimisation procedure for band selection ($B(\lambda)$).

Fig. 5. Canopy architecture of scenario 7 (top panels) and scenario 8 (bottom panels).

Table 2

Maximum tree height and height at which the albedometer is placed above the scene for each scenario and height increments.

Scenario	Max tree height (m)	Max albedo height (m)	Height increment
Scenarios 1–5	4.12	29.12	1 m (4.12–14.12 m) 5 m (14.12–29.12 m)
Scenario 6	11.28	39.28	1 m (11.28–21.28 m) 5 m (21.28–39.28 m)
Scenario 7	25.5	85.5	1 m (25.5–55.5 m) 10 m (55.5–85.5 m)
Scenario 8	25.5	125.5	1 m (25.5–55.5 m) 10 m (55.5–125.5 m)

5. Computing broadband albedo ($\alpha_{[\lambda_1, \lambda_2]}^{bba}$) under direct light illumination conditions (*DHR*) as the weighted sum of spectral albedo values at discrete spectral wavelengths (Eq. (2))

$$\alpha_{[\lambda_1, \lambda_2]}^{bba}(\theta, \phi) = \frac{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} \alpha(\lambda, \theta, \phi) \cdot E^{\downarrow}(\lambda) \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot SR(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} E^{\downarrow}(\lambda) \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot SR(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad (2)$$

The albedometers were placed every 10 cm within the scene in a grid at the top of the canopy, starting at the tallest tree height; 4.12 m for scenarios 1–5, 11.27 m for scenario 6, and 25.5 m for scenarios 7 and 8. This grid was then placed at incremental heights above the canopy, to allow investigation into the impact of height. The heights above the canopy were chosen based on the canopy, whereby the grid of albedometers was placed at greater heights above top-of-canopy (TOC) for scenarios 7 and 8,

in comparison to scenarios 1–6. Table 2 demonstrates the different heights considered for each canopy described in Section 2.2. An optimisation framework was developed to ensure that broadband albedo measured from a simulated albedometer could be computed to within 1% accuracy, defined by the number of rays N_{rays} used in each spectral wavelength. Given that the uncertainty of a Monte Carlo model (σ_{mc}) is described by $\sigma_{mc} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{rays}}}$, preliminary simulations of spectral albedo ($\alpha(\lambda, \theta, \phi)$) in 8 spectral bands (442 nm, 551 nm, 674 nm, 712 nm, 741 nm, 752 nm, 781 nm, 910 nm), using the voxel-flux measurements were made for the birchstand canopy introduced in Section 2.2, where a number of rays entering each voxel were varied. A reference simulation of spectral albedo ($\alpha_{ref}(\lambda, \theta, \phi)$) was made using 1,000,000 rays per voxel, where the placement of an albedometer every 10 cm in a 100×100 m scene constituted a total of 1,000,000 voxels, therefore a total of 10^{12} rays for the entire scene. The normalised relative uncertainty δ_N [%] between $\alpha_{ref}(\lambda, \theta, \phi)$ and $\alpha(\lambda, \theta, \phi)$ was computed using $\frac{\alpha_{ref}(\lambda, \theta, \phi) - \alpha(\lambda, \theta, \phi)}{\alpha_{ref}(\lambda, \theta, \phi)} \times 100$, and a linear relationship developed between δ_N and number of rays, N_{rays} , entering each voxel:

$$\log(\delta_N) = m \log(N_{rays}) + c \quad (3)$$

where m and c represent the slope and the intercept of the linear relationship. The slope m was found to be -0.5 for all spectral wavebands. Here, the intercept c represents the residual error, and was found to exhibit a linear relationship with spectral albedo: $c = 6.6376 - 12.4624 \cdot \alpha(\lambda, \theta, \phi)$. If the spectral albedo is known, the residual error c can be estimated, input into Eq. (3), and given a specified δ_N , the number of rays per voxel estimated for each spectral albedo. Accordingly, for each of the 125 spectral wavelengths, DHR $\alpha(\lambda, \theta, \phi)$ was simulated using **raytran** and then the number of rays per voxel required for simulations to be within 1% accuracy were computed. Total rays for the scene were computed as the product of the number of rays per voxel, and the number of voxels.

2.5. Quality assessment

The uncertainty of the simulated albedometer measurements was documented using the normalised relative uncertainty (δ) and the absolute normalised relative uncertainties ($|\delta|$). Both metrics were also expressed as a percentage [%], computed from $\delta \cdot 100$ and $|\delta| \cdot 100$. A reference albedo, α_{ref} , represents the broadband albedo computed by the convolution of DHR simulated by **raytran** and solar spectral irradiance in 400–2500 nm spectral domain at spectral intervals of 5 nm using:

$$\alpha_{ref} = \frac{\int_{400}^{2500} \alpha(\lambda, \theta, \phi) E^{\downarrow}(\lambda) d(\lambda)}{\int_{400}^{2500} E^{\downarrow}(\lambda) d(\lambda)} \quad (4)$$

Uncertainty metrics are therefore computed using:

$$\delta = \frac{\alpha_{ref} - \alpha_{[\lambda_1, \lambda_2]}^{bba}(\theta, \phi)}{\alpha_{ref}} \quad (5)$$

$$|\delta| = \frac{|\alpha_{ref} - \alpha_{[\lambda_1, \lambda_2]}^{bba}(\theta, \phi)|}{\alpha_{ref}} \quad (6)$$

The above uncertainty metrics were computed at each albedometer simulation at a given height, constituting an albedometer simulation and associated uncertainty every 10 cm within a canopy at a given height. Various aggregated uncertainty statistics were computed. The first was simply the arithmetic mean $\langle \delta \rangle$ ($\langle |\delta| \rangle$) of δ ($|\delta|$) of all N albedometer simulations, defined in this study as 1,000,000 (10^5) simulations:

$$\langle \delta \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^{10^5} \delta \quad (7)$$

The remaining aggregated uncertainty statistics were based on the 68th, 95th and 99th percentiles (i.e. the first, second and third standard deviations) taken from a histogram of δ (δ_{68} , δ_{95} , δ_{99}) and $|\delta|$ ($|\delta|_{68}$, $|\delta|_{95}$, $|\delta|_{99}$), indicating the normalised difference uncertainty level that encompasses 68%, 95% or 99% of the data. For the purpose of this study, compliance with WMO 3% requirement for in situ albedometer measurements was tested against uncertainty statistics.

3. Results

3.1. Citrus orchard canopy (scenario 2)

Results are first shown for the citrus orchard canopy with a solar azimuth angle of 0° , whereby the sun is shining across the canopy rows, and a solar zenith angle of 20° (scenario 2). Fig. 6 represents the simulated in situ measurements with respect to height, where 0 m TOC implies 0 m top-of-canopy, and top-of-canopy is defined as the maximum tree height of all the trees within the scene. From here on, 0 m TOC will be referred to as 0 m, where any height that is mentioned, unless explicitly stated, signifies the height above the canopy top. At 0 m, the simulated albedometer directly measures the albedo of the scene element below it, where the alternating tree and soil row structure is clearly evident. Over the tree rows, BBA is measured lower than over the soil background, and in areas where gaps in the row structure occur, the albedometer measures high albedo values.

When the albedometer is placed at 1 m above the canopy, these structural impacts start to become less dominant, where the albedometer measures albedo from an increasing number of elements within the scene, rather than those directly below it. As height is increased further above the canopy, the variability in albedometer measurements resulting from the canopy structure is further reduced. At 3–5 m, and to some extent 10 m, the impact of gaps in the row structure is still slightly evident with patches of higher albedo values, but beyond 15 m, the albedometer is high enough to measure approximately the average albedo of the scene.

To view the spatial distribution of uncertainty values, δ [%] were taken at each in situ measurement, as shown in Fig. 7. At 0 m, positive uncertainties occur over the tree

Fig. 6. Spatial representation of albedo measured by simulated albedometer for a citrus orchard canopy at incremental heights above the canopy. Each measurement represents a 10 cm size albedometer, thus an albedometer simulation is made every 10 cm at a specific height.

rows, implying an overestimation of albedo, whereas negative uncertainties occur over soil, implying an underestimation of albedo. Where gaps in the tree rows occur, large areas of negative uncertainties dominate. As height is increased to 1 m, the pronounced differences between the trees and soil become less prominent, where the uncertainties appear less variable. As height is further increased, the variability in uncertainties as a result of the canopy structure, until the structure is no longer evident.

Next, the uncertainties are computed for simulations at each height, following Eqs. (5)–(6) outlined in Section 2.4. Histograms were computed of the absolute relative normalised uncertainty ($|\delta|$) (Fig. 8), allowing the calculation of the mean, 68th percentile (1σ), 95th percentile (2σ) and 99th percentile (3σ) uncertainties ($\langle|\delta|\rangle$, $|\delta|_{68}$, $|\delta|_{95}$ and $|\delta|_{99}$). The histograms indicate that with increasing height, the spread of uncertainties values decreases, as do the uncertainties values themselves.

To further examine the impact of height on uncertainty values, the absolute histograms shown in Fig. 8 were recalculated as a percentage ($|\delta|$) [%], and the mean ($\langle|\delta|\rangle$) and 68th ($|\delta|_{68}$), 95th ($|\delta|_{95}$) and 99th ($|\delta|_{99}$) percentiles taken at each height, demonstrated in Fig. 9.

Focusing firstly on the mean values, at 0 m, $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ is greatest at 3.94%, i.e. at 0 m above the canopy, an in situ measurement within the scene would have a mean uncertainty values of 3.94% or lower. As height is increased, $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ decreases until 25 m, where uncertainty is measured at 2.24%. The grey area in Fig. 9 represents the WMO requirement for in situ measurements of albedo to be within 3%, therefore on average, once the albedometer is placed 2 m above the canopy, the WMO requirement can be reached. If the 68th percentile is now considered, at 0 m, an $|\delta|_{68}$ of 5.76% implies that 68% of the in situ measurements within the scene would have an uncertainty value of 5.76% or less. As height increases, $|\delta|_{68}$ follows the same pattern as the mean, however it does not reach the WMO requirement at 25 m, instead reaching a minimum uncertainty of 3.295%. Again the 95th and 99th percentiles do not reach the WMO requirement with a minimum uncertainty of 6.51% and 8.66% respectively.

3.2. Citrus orchard: illumination angle (scenarios 1–4)

Results for illumination angle are represented in Fig. 10. Two azimuth angles are investigated: 90° with a zenith

Fig. 7. Spatial representation of relative normalised uncertainties (δ) [%] for each simulated albedometer at specific heights above the citrus orchard canopy.

angle of 20° (scenario 4) and 0° with three zenith angles 0°, 20° and 50° (scenarios 1, 2 and 3 respectively). 0° represents when the sun is shining across the row, and 90° where the sun is shining down the rows (Fig. 2). All illumination angles exhibit a similar pattern to that described in Section 3.1; at 0 m, uncertainties are greatest and then decrease with height. However, with SAA and SZA at nadir (0°), both $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ and $|\delta|_{95}$ of the in situ simulations are smaller than for other angles at 0 m at 3.21% and 9.17% respectively (blue lines). As the zenith angle is increased to 20° and the azimuth angle kept at 0° (green lines), $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ and $|\delta|_{95}$ increase to 3.94% and 11.12%, and at a zenith angle of 50° (yellow lines), further increased to 6.48% and 18.22% respectively. Hence, as the solar zenith angle increases while the azimuth angle stays at 0°, at 0 m, uncertainties increase. As height is then increased above the canopy, for all zenith angles the uncertainty decreases, where for higher solar zenith angles, this decrease in uncertainty is more pronounced.

In terms of the WMO requirement, 3% is reached at similar heights for SAA 0° and SZA of 0° and 20°; 1 m and 2 m above the canopy respectively. For a SZA of 50°, height

is required to be ~7 m above the canopy in order to reach the WMO requirement. At 25 m, $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ is well within WMO requirement for each SZA, with values of 2.22% (0°), 2.23% (20°) and 2.73% (50°). For all canopies with uncertainty computed from the 95th percentile, the WMO requirement of 3% is not met.

If the azimuth angle is rotated 90° from 0° to 90°, where the sun is now shining down the row, with a SZA of 20°, two observations can be made. Firstly, in comparison to an azimuth angle of 0° and SZA of 20°, both $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ and $|\delta|_{95}$ at 0 m are smaller at 3.88% and 10.94% respectively. However, as the albedometer is placed higher above the top of the canopy, both $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ and $|\delta|_{95}$ do not reduce as much as when the SAA is 0°, where the 3% requirement is not met, but stays at 3.23%.

3.3. Citrus orchard: canopy structure (scenarios 5 and 6)

Fig. 11 represents uncertainty with height for scenario 3, and for the scenarios described in Section 2.2 where trees are removed to lessen the impact of the row structure (scenario 5) and tree height is increased (scenario 6).

Fig. 8. Histogram of absolute relative normalised uncertainties ($|\delta|$) for N number of albedometers ($N=1,000,000$) at a specific height above the canopy with the associated mean, 68th, 95th and 99th percentile uncertainties ($\langle|\delta|\rangle$, $|\delta|_{68}$, $|\delta|_{95}$ and $|\delta|_{99}$).

For all canopies, SAA was 0° , in order to evaluate shadowing impacts of the row structure, and a SZA of 50° (i.e. the angular configuration which has the highest uncertainties as found in Section 3.2).

Fig. 11 demonstrates that at all heights, uncertainties are greater for this scenario in comparison to scenario 3. At 0 m, uncertainties are 8.03% and 23.09% for $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ and $|\delta|_{95}$ respectively, in comparison to 6.48% and 18.22% for scenario 3. Uncertainties reduce with height like other scenarios, however mean uncertainty does not pass the WMO

requirement but almost reaches the requirement at 3.16%, whereas for scenario 3, the WMO requirement is reached at ~ 7 m.

Fig. 11 shows that for scenario 6, at 0 m, $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ and $|\delta|_{95}$ are 9.57% and 24.16% respectively; greater than scenario 3. Hence, at 0 m, an increase in tree height leads to an increase in uncertainty. $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ and $|\delta|_{95}$ then follow the same pattern as explained previously for the citrus orchard canopy, whereby uncertainty decreases with height above the canopy. The decrease in uncertainty is very

pronounced for this scenario with taller trees, but for $\langle|\delta|\rangle$, WMO requirement is met at the same height (~ 7 m) as scenario 3. Following Sections 3.1 and 3.2, for the 95th percentile uncertainties, the WMO requirement is not met at any height.

3.4. Birchstand canopy (scenario 7)

This section, and the section following, describe results obtained for the birchstand canopy in both summer (scenario 7) and winter (scenario 8) seasons. Fig. 12 represents simulated albedometer measurements at 9 different heights, starting at 0 m and ending at 40 m for the birchstand during summer canopy. As before, low albedo values represent albedo over forested area and high albedo values over soil.

At 0 m, gaps within the canopy are evident in areas where local albedo values are high, demonstrated by the

Fig. 9. Absolute relative normalized uncertainty [%] with respect to height above the citrus orchard canopy for the mean, 68th, 95th and 99th percentile uncertainty values ($\langle|\delta|\rangle$, $|\delta|_{68}$, $|\delta|_{95}$ and $|\delta|_{99}$) taken from histogram of uncertainty values. The gray shaded area represents WMO 3% requirement.

brighter yellow-brown circular patches within the canopy. As height is increased above the canopy to 1 m, as with the citrus canopy, the structural impacts of the canopy start to become less dominant, whereby the high albedo values found in gaps within the canopy become less extreme. As the albedometer is placed higher above the canopy, the variability in the albedometer measurements is increasingly reduced as the impact of canopy structure on the local albedo measurement is reduced. At 40 m, it is clear that canopy structure no longer impacts the measurement of albedo. At this height, no matter where the albedometer is placed within the scene, the albedometer appears not to measure the local albedo values but rather, the average albedo.

If spatial uncertainties are now considered, one can see the impacts of canopy structural effects with respect to height in Fig. 13. At 0 m, where gaps appear within the canopy and soil dominates the local albedometer measurement, albedo is measured with large negative uncertainties (blueish colour), hence albedo is consistently underestimated. Over parts of the canopy dominated by the trees, local albedo measurements are associated with large positive uncertainties (reddish colour), and albedo is consistently overestimated. As the albedometer is placed higher above the canopy, uncertainties begin to converge towards zero for areas dominated by both soil and tree material, as the albedometer measures more the average albedo of the scene rather than the local albedo. For this canopy, up to 20 m, positive uncertainties appear to be concentrated in the middle of the scene and negative uncertainties on the edges of the canopy. This is a result of the canopy design, whereby the canopy described by RAMI-IV places a soil border around the scene. However at 40 m and above, this impact is negligible.

Fig. 14 demonstrates that for $\langle|\delta|\rangle$, at 0 m, uncertainty is computed at 5.14%. As height increases, uncertainties values decrease very slowly in comparison to the previous citrus canopies. WMO requirement is not reached until 60 m TOC (i.e 85.5 m height), with an uncertainty of 2.97%. The behaviour of this canopy in the reduction of

Fig. 10. Mean and 95th percentile absolute relative normalized uncertainties ($\langle|\delta|\rangle$ and $|\delta|_{95}$) [%] with respect to height for different illumination scenarios simulated for citrus orchard canopy (scenarios 1–4). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure, the reader is referred to the web version of this paper.)

Fig. 11. Mean (left panel) and 95th percentile (right panel) absolute relative normalised uncertainties ($|\delta|$ and $|\delta|_{95}$) [%] with respect to height for scenario 3 (blue line) which represents the original canopy, scenario 5 (red line) and scenario 6 (green line). The grey area represents the WMO 3% requirement. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure caption, the reader is referred to the web version of this paper.)

Fig. 12. Spatial representation of albedo measured by simulated albedometer for a birchstand summer canopy (scenario 7) at incremental heights above the canopy.

Fig. 13. Spatial representation of relative normalised uncertainties (δ) [%] for each simulated albedometer at specific heights above the birchstand summer canopy (scenario 7). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure, the reader is referred to the web version of this paper.)

uncertainty with height deviates slightly away from the theoretical expectation exhibited in the previous canopies (i.e. smooth decrease). This could be due the canopy structure, as this canopy has ‘tracks’ of soil running through the canopy and areas that are not fully covered by vegetation, causing large variability between parts of the canopy that are fully vegetated and parts that are exposed to soil. As a result, at certain heights, it is possible that on average the albedometer measures more from a vegetated or exposed soil area. If the remaining percentiles are considered, particularly for the 99th percentile, this is even clearer, where instead of a smooth decrease in uncertainty, discrepancies occur at specific heights, principally from 8 m to 20 m. As with previous canopies, the 68th, 95th and 99th percentiles do not reach the WMO requirement.

3.5. Birchstand winter canopy (scenario 8)

Fig. 15 demonstrates uncertainties with respect to height for this canopy. For this scenario, considering firstly $\langle|\delta|\rangle$, at 0 m, uncertainty is computed at 6.3%, which is higher than that computed during the summer season. As the albedometer is placed higher above the canopy,

uncertainties are reduced quite dramatically, until 100 m, where uncertainty is measured at 0.24%. WMO requirement is passed at 17 m, which is lower than the summer season. However, the most apparent feature for this canopy is that although at 0 m, uncertainties for each of the percentiles are greater, as height is increased, $\langle|\delta|\rangle$, $|\delta|_{68}$, $|\delta|_{95}$ and $|\delta|_{99}$ converge, which is not evident in any of the canopies previously mentioned. In addition, the WMO requirement is passed at all percentiles, albeit at different heights: 23 m, 33 m and 38 m for the 68th, 95th and 99th percentiles respectively.

3.6. Multiple albedometers

The data were also analysed to explore the potential benefits of using multiple albedometers. At each height for each albedometer measurement another random albedometer measurement in a different spatial position was chosen, and the albedo calculated as the mean of the two measurements. This procedure was conducted for up to 20 albedometers (i.e. given the base albedometer position, up to 20 other randomly placed albedometers were used to compute the mean albedo between the measurements),

Fig. 14. Absolute relative normalised uncertainty [%] with respect to height above the birchstand summer canopy (scenario 7) for the mean, 68th, 95th and 99th percentile uncertainty values ($\langle|\delta|\rangle$, $|\delta|_{68}$, $|\delta|_{95}$ and $|\delta|_{99}$). The gray shaded area represents WMO 3% requirement.

Fig. 15. Absolute relative normalised uncertainty [%] with respect to height above the birchstand winter canopy (scenario 8) for the mean, 68th, 95th and 99th percentile uncertainty values ($\langle|\delta|\rangle$, $|\delta|_{68}$, $|\delta|_{95}$ and $|\delta|_{99}$). The gray shaded area represents WMO 3% requirement.

for every albedometer simulation at every height. Uncertainty statistics were then computed based on Eq. (6) as a percentage (the absolute relative normalised uncertainty); $|\delta|$ as percentage, for $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ and $|\delta|_{95}$. Results in Fig. 16 indicate the aggregated uncertainty metrics with respect to number of albedometers, where the grey shaded area represents the WMO requirement, to assess if multiple albedometers can be useful method for reaching this requirement. For both $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ and $|\delta|_{95}$ (dotted line) the height at 0 m, the maximum height in which the albedometer is placed above the canopy and the most likely height used in the field for this type of canopy (based on expert knowledge) is demonstrated. For all canopies, it is clear that simply adding 1 more albedometer within the canopy can significantly reduce the uncertainty, particularly when the albedometer is placed lower above the canopy.

Considering that at the maximum height the albedometer is placed above the canopy, most scenarios are within the

WMO requirement already (with exception to scenario 5) for $\langle|\delta|\rangle$, therefore multiple albedometers only reduce $\langle|\delta|\rangle$ further within the requirement. For scenario 5, adding an additional albedometer allows the requirement to be met. For most scenarios, the maximum height and height likely used in the field exhibit similar uncertainty values, and therefore respond similarly to addition albedometers. However for the scenarios 5 and 7, where the likely values used in the field show uncertainty values that do not meet the WMO requirement, adding 1 extra albedometer reduces the uncertainty to meet the requirement. For all scenarios, the uncertainties no longer decrease once a certain number of albedometers is reached, generally above 10 albedometers, and uncertainties for maximum and field heights tend to converge as the number of albedometers is increased.

The benefit of using multiple albedometers becomes more apparent if $|\delta|_{95}$ is used. As explained previously, using the 95th percentile often means the WMO requirement is not met, however Fig. 16 indicates that for the maximum and most likely used in the field albedometer heights above the canopy, adding 2–3 albedometers can, in most scenarios, allow the requirement to be met. At 0 m above the canopy, while uncertainties are still reduced, only in scenarios 1 and 2, can the requirement be met with 8 and 13 albedometers respectively. For the remaining scenarios, the requirement can still not be met at 0 m with 20 albedometers.

4. Discussion

4.1. Placement of albedometer within the canopy

Results indicate that the placement of albedometer is coupled with the canopy structure. One of the most significant contributions towards uncertainty in in situ measurements, and also one of the main issues when comparing in situ with EO albedo products, is landscape heterogeneity, and the representativeness of one single albedo measurement [4]. Results from this study suggest that a large range of uncertainties can be encountered in the placement of the albedometer, particularly at low heights above the canopy, and that an in situ albedo measurement computed from a single albedometer could provide a biased estimate of albedo at the pixel scale, and can therefore impact intercomparison and validation with EO albedo products. Generally if the albedometer is placed over an area of canopy with foliage elements, high absorption of radiation in the broadband contributes to the measurement of low albedo by the albedometer, whereas less absorption in the broadband by soil causes the measurement high albedo values over areas dominated by soil. As a result, positive uncertainties are generally found over foliage elements and negative uncertainties found over areas of soil.

Canopy κ_{red} and fractional coverage values are controlling factors in the variability in the measurement of albedo. Variability in the uncertainties in the placement of the albedometer are greatest for the birchstand canopy, where a κ_{red} of > 1 indicates that the canopy is clumped and heterogeneous. On the other hand, while κ_{red} for the

Fig. 16. Mean and 95th percentile absolute relative normalised uncertainty ($|\delta|$ and $|\delta|_{99}$) [%] for number of albedometers used to compute albedo, with the grey shaded area representing the WMO 3% requirement. Scenarios 1, 2, 3, 5, 6 and 7 are shown.

citrus canopies indicated a highly clumped canopy (with a value of 1.511) as a result of the row planting structure, this canopy has a lower fractional coverage, in addition to lower tree heights, and therefore spatial uncertainties for this canopy are smaller than the heterogeneous birchstand canopy. This is likely due to a smaller variation in local LAD/LAI values (between foliage and soil) in the citrus canopy, hence it is necessary to consider κ_{red} in conjunction with LAD and fractional coverage when analysing the impact of canopy structure on uncertainties resulting from the placement of albedometer within the canopy.

4.2. Height of albedometer

The height of the albedometer above the canopy is one of the controlling factors of uncertainty, and has been demonstrated to determine whether uncertainties in the in situ measurement can reach a certain requirement. The 4 different aggregated uncertainty statistics (mean and 68th, 95th and 99th percentiles) indicate the uncertainty within which a percentage of the uncertainties for individual albedometer measurements would fall within. In general, uncertainties reduce with height rapidly until a point, then increasing the height only has a small impact on reducing the uncertainties. This pattern can be interpreted as follows. At 0 m above the canopy, the albedometer field-of-view (FOV) is very small, so that it measures the properties of the element directly below it. This is best demonstrated in the citrus orchard canopies, whereby the impact of alternating soil and foliage rows are clearly observed in Figs. 6 and 9 as the albedometer directly measures the albedo of either soil or foliage. As the measurement of albedo is very variable at 0 m, the uncertainties are therefore large, as few albedometers measure the 'reference' albedo of the scene, and rather measure the contributions to albedo from separate elements within the scene. As height is increased above the canopy, the FOV of the albedometer is increased so that it measures the albedo of more elements in the scene, and is therefore able to measure more the reference albedo of the canopy. Accordingly, as height is increased, a single albedometer is able to provide a less biased estimate of albedo with respect to the reference or pixel albedo. Once a certain height is reached such that the FOV is large enough to measure the true albedo of the canopy, increasing the height has little impact on the uncertainties.

In this study, uncertainties associated with height above the canopy were investigated with respect to the WMO 3% requirement. For the mean uncertainty, each canopy reaches the requirement at a different height, or in the case of a citrus orchard canopy with 20% of tree removed, not at all. For the remaining percentiles, the requirement is often not reached, with the exception of the birchstand winter canopy, which is an open sparse canopy with $\kappa_{red} < 1$ and low fractional coverage and LAD. The height at which the requirement can be reached clearly depends on the canopy structure and the tree heights comprised in the canopy. It would be useful to investigate if a standard height above the canopy with respect to the tree heights included in the canopy could be achieved, for example the albedometer should be placed x

Fig. 17. Mean absolute relative normalised uncertainty ($\langle |\delta| \rangle$) [%] with respect to albedometer height above the canopy normalised for the maximum tree height within the canopy for all scenarios, with WMO 3% requirement indicated by the grey shaded area.

times the maximum tree height above the canopy. To achieve this, heights were normalised with respect to the maximum tree height within the canopies, to explore if a standard height above the canopy can be reached. It was expected that perhaps a common height normalised to the maximum tree height could be found, however Fig. 17 indicates this is not the case. Fig. 17 suggests that uncertainty associated with the placement of the albedometer above the scene is highly subjective to the canopy and solar angle configuration, and therefore in order to respect a given requirement, whether it be the WMO requirement or a user-defined requirement, the placement of albedometer above the canopy with respect to the maximum tree height will depend also on canopy structural parameters such as landscape heterogeneity, LAD and fractional coverage, in addition to illumination angle, and cannot be evaluated based solely on the tree heights within the canopy. In consequence, to reach a requirement, the placement of the albedometer above a canopy appears entirely scenario-dependent, and should be reviewed on a case-by-case basis.

4.3. Canopy structure

Ecosystem type and canopy structure, defined by LAD, fractional coverage and κ_{red} , have a crucial impact on both the measurement of albedo within a canopy, and also their associated uncertainties. In a boreal deciduous forest such as the birchstand forest, which is defined by high LAI but relatively low LAD, and fractional coverage and a κ_{red} value > 1 that indicates a clumped heterogeneous canopy structure, variation in local albedo measurements are large. This is a result of the highly clumped structure of the canopy, contributing to distinct areas of foliage and soil, which causes large variations in the local albedo measured over foliage and over soil. Thus, through a combined number of factors, uncertainties are large for such a boreal deciduous forest. With respect to the WMO requirement,

3% is not reached until 60 m above the canopy. In the field for such a canopy, a height of approximately 30 m is used for an albedometer. At 30 m while the uncertainty is relatively small at 3.4%, results from this study perhaps indicate that this height is not suitable for an albedometer measurement to be within 3%.

κ_{red} heterogeneity index is high (1.511) for the citrus canopies as a result of the clumped row structure, as is LAD (resulting from the structure of citrus trees which have a consistently high LAD along the vertical profile of the tree plus a small trunk), however fractional coverage is not high compared to the birchstand canopy, and tree heights, and variation in tree heights within the canopy are low, thus the citrus canopies exhibit smaller uncertainties. While at 0 m uncertainties can be fairly large, as height is increased, uncertainties are reduced significantly, reaching the WMO requirement at low heights above the canopy. This indicates that it is likely that tree heights within the canopy, fractional coverage and local LAI values control the magnitude of the uncertainties, whereas κ_{red} and average LAI/LAD control the rate at which uncertainties reduce with increasing height placement of the albedometer above the canopy. However, scenario 5, a scenario that reduces the amount of trees within the citrus canopy by 20%, indicates that if a canopy is a clumped canopy with $\kappa_{red} > 1$ but the fractional coverage is low, results appear somewhat counter-intuitive. It was expected that as trees have been removed and increased areas of soil exposed, uncertainties might decrease, however it appears there is an optimal fractional coverage of vegetation within the scene, and beyond this, an in situ albedometer measurement provides a more biased estimate of albedo. In their intercomparison between in situ and MODIS albedo retrievals, Cescatti et al. [4] find large differences between in situ and MODIS retrievals of albedo in cropland and grassland ecosystem types, ascribed to the spatial variability in LAI and the variability in exposed soil, in addition to responses to climate drivers and management practices. While the citrus orchard canopy is not exactly cropland nor grassland, the spatial variability in LAI and areas with exposed soil still exist, and therefore increasing this variability in LAI and exposing more soil when 20% of the trees are removed is likely the reason behind this increase in uncertainty. Moreover, the impact of shadowing must also be considered. In this case a SZA of 50° was used, which causes large shadowing impacts over the soil. As increasing areas of soil are exposed when 20% of the trees are removed, gaps within the trees are increased, and can exacerbate the impact of shadowing on uncertainties. Finally, it is interesting to note that for a birchstand winter canopy, which has a slightly higher fractional coverage of 0.251, compared to 0.230 for scenario 5, uncertainties meet the WMO requirement and almost reduce to 0% when the albedometer is placed at large heights above the canopy. Clearly an optimal fractional coverage of vegetation within the scene can only be considered if the canopy has a clumped heterogeneous structure ($\kappa_{red} > 1$) which contains foliage, i.e. the LAI cannot be close to 0.

In terms of tree height, the κ_{red} parameter for scenario 6 suggests the canopy moves from a clumped

heterogeneous structure ($\kappa_{red}=1.511$) to a closed canopy ($\kappa_{red}=0.421$), which removes the impacts of shadowing, as the tree crowns obscure more of the canopy gaps and soil. The impact of tree height on uncertainties can be interpreted as follows; when an albedometer is placed at lower heights above the canopy, if the canopy contains taller trees, such as scenario 6, or the birchstand canopy, uncertainties are large. However, as the albedometer is placed higher above the canopy, the tree heights have less an impact until eventually uncertainties converge with the original canopy. Therefore the reduced impact in shadowing and increased coverage of the canopy (i.e. reducing local variations in foliage and soil) counter-effects the higher uncertainties resulting from increased tree height. This is demonstrated when the WMO requirement is met with an albedometer placed at exactly the same height above the canopy for the canopy with increased tree height in comparison to the original canopy with lower tree heights.

4.4. Seasonality

The impact of changing seasonality was investigated using a boreal deciduous forest in both summer and winter seasons. During winter, a deciduous canopy such as the birchstand canopy based on measurements in Estonia, loses its foliage and the soil/understorey is covered with snow. The loss of foliage reduces the κ_{red} parameter so that the canopy moves from a clumped heterogeneous canopy in the summer to a more open sparse tree coverage with a lower LAD and fractional coverage, resulting in a reduction in uncertainties in Fig. 15. From 0 to 10 m TOC, uncertainties are slightly greater than that of the summer canopy, likely resulting from the assumption that the snow surface is a lambertian scatterer, thus light is diffusely scattered with high reflectance properties associated with snow, and may cause high local differences between albedometers 10 cm apart. However, beyond 10 m uncertainties continue to reduce whereas during the summer season, this reduction in uncertainty is significantly less defined. As height is increased, uncertainty converges towards 0%. Most importantly for this canopy, all uncertainties for all percentiles converge towards 0%. While at 0 m uncertainties are increasingly larger for the 68th, 95th and 99th percentiles, they all tend towards 0% once 100 m is reached. Considering no other canopy exhibited this behaviour, it is likely that the lack of canopy structure is the reason behind the percentiles converging. The differences between summer and winter canopies clearly indicate that season can have a significant impact on the uncertainties, whether reducing or increasing.

4.5. Illumination angle

In situ albedometer measurements are generally taken in the hour that centres the solar noon [4], however this study suggests that this decision can impact the uncertainty of the in situ measurement, particularly in canopies that are composed of many gaps within the canopy or a row structure such as the citrus orchard canopy. The result of shadowing from changing illumination angle produces

large variability in the albedo measurements, and therefore increases uncertainties, particularly at lower heights above the canopy. This is particularly true in the case of a regular row planting structure, indicated by the citrus orchard canopy. When SAA is such that the sun is shining across the rows (in this case with an azimuth angle of 0°), increasing zenith angle spreads the shadow from the tree rows further into the row gaps. This increase in shadow over the soil gaps signifies a more biased estimate of the albedo from one single albedometer, as demonstrated in Fig. 10. Accordingly, in scenarios where an illumination angle at nadir corresponds to the solar noon, current practices of albedometer measurements at solar noon estimate albedo with the smallest uncertainties. If the illumination angle does not correspond to nadir at solar noon, then it is likely that shadowing effects will influence the uncertainties.

4.6. Choice of uncertainty percentile

Results indicate that the choice of uncertainty percentile can hugely impact the quality assessment of in situ albedo measurements. For percentiles of 68%, 95% and 99%, WMO requirement was not met in most of the scenarios introduced in this study, which might suggest that for canopies with an inherent level of complexity, the WMO requirement is indeed too stringent, and that if the uncertainty percentile must be above the mean, then the WMO requirement must be adjusted to account for this. The point that this suggestion only applied in canopies with an ‘inherent level of complexity’ must be reinforced, as it is clear from the birchstand winter canopy, which is a very simple canopy structure with all deciduous foliage elements removed, uncertainties for the mean and the percentiles converge at a certain height. However for all remaining canopies with foliage elements, WMO requirement is not met, and therefore suggests that for canopies with a complex foliage structure within the trees, the WMO requirement for 3% is difficult to meet if percentiles of 68%, 95% and 99% must be used.

4.7. Multiple albedometers

An experiment on the potential benefits of using multiple albedometers demonstrated that in all canopies, using two albedometers was shown to significantly reduce uncertainties. Results indicated that the WMO requirement (or any other requirement) can be met more easily if two or more albedometers can be used to compute albedo of a canopy, or a pixel. Results here suggest that for scenarios with $\kappa_{red} > 1$, and high associated LAI and fractional coverage, such as the birchstand canopy, multiple measurements can indeed be useful to reduce the uncertainty of the in situ measurement, particularly if the albedometer must be placed at a height above the canopy in which the WMO (or another) requirement cannot be met. For example in the birchstand canopy, at 30 m above the canopy (the

height at which recommendations have been made for a canopy such as this) the WMO requirement is not quite met, however simply using an extra albedometer can reduce the mean uncertainty to within the requirement. On the other hand, in canopies where $\kappa_{red} > 1$, but fractional coverage is low, causing high spatial variability in the LAI, such as the citrus canopy with 20% of trees randomly removed, uncertainties were also demonstrated not to reach the WMO requirement even at the maximum height above the canopy. Multiple albedometers were proven to be useful also in these cases, where using 2 albedometers was shown to reduce mean uncertainty to within the WMO requirement.

While the mean uncertainty generally is able to meet the WMO requirement at heights commonly used in the field with even one albedometer for most of the canopies, this is not the case for the 68th, 95th and 99th percentiles. The use of multiple albedometers is strengthened when these percentiles are considered, as demonstrated by the 95th percentile in Fig. 16. For the citrus canopies, at heights commonly used in the field, using between 2 and 5 in situ measurements can reduce the 95th percentile uncertainty to be within the WMO requirement. For the birchstand canopy due to κ_{red} value > 1 , i.e. clumped heterogeneous canopy structure and large tree heights, up to 10 albedometers would be needed to reach a 3% requirement, with an uncertainty percentile of 95%.

4.8. Accuracy requirement

In this study we have focused on the WMO 3% requirement, and how potential sources of uncertainty influence if this requirement can be met or not. Results indicate that in certain scenarios, the 3% requirement is perhaps too stringent, particularly in canopies with higher fractional coverage values associated with a clumped heterogeneous structure or in canopies that have high LAD and high spatial variability in LAI as a result of low fractional coverage in a canopy with a highly clumped structure. However, the aim of this study was not just to assess if the WMO requirement can or cannot be met, but also to show that this framework for the quality assessment of albedo is designed so that any requirement (or tolerance interval) may be defined by a user, and then tested. In addition this study has aimed to demonstrate that while the WMO requirement appears to be appropriate for some canopies, and not for others, it can be possible to apply different requirements for different ecosystem types and canopy complexities, if it is useful for the user. If the WMO requirement is not required, a model-based framework such as the one presented in this study can provide recommendations on the choice of a requirement under a specific protocol (i.e. placement of albedometer within and above the canopy) and under the scenario factors, i.e. canopy structure (LAD, fractional coverage and heterogeneity), ecosystem type, illumination angle and season.

5. Conclusions

In this study we have presented a novel model-based quality assessment framework for in situ measurements of albedo that uses a 3D Monte Carlo Ray Tracing (MCRT) model to simulate the field measurements of surface albedo, to identify the main contributions to uncertainty and to test compliance with the WMO requirement for accuracy of in situ albedo measurements to be of use for the validation of EO products. The primary contributions towards uncertainties were the placement of the albedometer within the canopy, height of the albedometer above the canopy and the combined impact of landscape heterogeneity (κ_{red}), LAD/LAI and fractional coverage. Uncertainties were proven also to depend on the season, particularly in deciduous forests, where the change from a clumped heterogeneous canopy to open tree coverage in summer and winter seasons respectively is critical. Illumination angle in a row planting structured canopy was shown to impact uncertainties as a result of shadowing effects, however only when the albedometer is placed at low heights above the canopy. At higher heights above the canopy, these effects are small. A study on the benefits of using multiple albedometers indicated that simply adding 1 extra albedometer could reduce uncertainties considerably, and can be useful firstly if confidence intervals of 95% or 99% uncertainty percentile are required, or secondly for either complex canopies or canopies with low fractional coverage.

The WMO requirement can be met for most canopy scenarios, however in the case of a complex birchstand canopy with clumped heterogeneous structure and high fractional coverage, the requirement cannot be met unless the albedometer is placed very high above the canopy. On the other hand, if a canopy is not significantly covered by foliage, results indicate that the WMO requirement also cannot be met, particularly when the albedometer is placed at the height above the canopy as operated in the field. In addition, the choice of uncertainty percentile is imperative in terms of the WMO requirement, as 95% or 99% intervals imply that WMO requirement is increasingly more difficult to comply to. While in this study we focused mainly on the WMO requirement, a valuable advantage of the framework that has been developed is that any requirement can be tested.

Further work should be carried out to develop the framework for additional ecosystem types, such that the main land surface cover types are encompassed. While the 3D canopies used are some of the most complex canopies available for MCRT modelling of vegetation, gaps still exist in some of the information provided, specifically the structure and spectral site characteristics. As increasingly realist scenes can be made that better reconstruct actual sites, this framework can be further improved to estimate uncertainties in sites that match both satellite-based and in situ observations even more.

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